

**DEVELOPMENT OF KELVAR/SAWDUST REINFORCED
POLYPROPYLENE BLEND HYBRID COMPOSITE FOR HIGH IMPACT
APPLICATION**

BY

**SHITTU-GBEKO, Ilias Olakunle
2017/1/69053EL**

**DEPARTMENT OF MATERIALS AND METALLURGICAL
ENGINEERING
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, MINNA**

JANUARY, 2024

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**A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF MATERIALS
AND METALLURGICAL ENGINEERING,
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, MINNA
IN PARTIAL FUFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF BACHELOR OF ENGINEERING (B.ENG) DEGREE IN
MATERIALS AND METALLURGICAL ENGINEERING**

JANUARY, 2024

DECLARATION

I SHITTU-GBEKO, Ilias Olakunle with matriculation number 2017/1/69053EL, Department of Materials and Metallurgical Engineering, School of Infrastructure, process Engineering and Technology. Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, hereby declare that this project work titled "**Development of Kevlar/Sawdust reinforced Polypropylene blend hybrid Composite for High Impact Application**" was carried out by me and has not been presented anywhere either for publication or award of any degree under the supervision of Engr. Prof. A.S Abdulrahman. All information utilized and their sources have been duly acknowledged.

SHITTU-GBEKO, Ilias Olakunle
2017/1/69053EL

Signature and Date

DEDICATION

All praise and thanks are due to Allah, the Creator, the Bestower of strength, wisdom, and knowledge. I dedicate this project to His glory, acknowledging that He has been my support and guide throughout this journey. It is by His grace that I have gained strength and found inspiration. I humbly submit this work as an expression of gratitude for His blessings and mercy.

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project titled "**Development of Kevlar/Sawdust Reinforced Polypropylene Blend Hybrid Composite for High Impact Application**" was carried out by Shittu-Gbeko Ilias Olakunle with the matriculation number 2017/1/69053EL under supervision of Engr. Prof A.S Abdulrahman, submitted to the department of Materials and Metallurgical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Minna in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Engineering (B.Eng.) Degree in Materials and Metallurgical Engineering.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I express my deepest gratitude to the Almighty Allah, the creator of the universe, for granting me health and clarity throughout this study. My heartfelt appreciation goes to Engr. Prof. A.S Abdulrahman, whose steadfast guidance and unwavering support have been invaluable in steering this project from its inception to its completion. I am immensely grateful to the Materials and Metallurgical Engineering Department, led by Engr. Prof. R.A. Muriana and supported by Engr. Prof. O.K. Abubakre, for their collective contributions to my academic journey.

Special thanks to Mr. and Mrs. Shittu-Gbeko, my brothers, for their unwavering moral and material support. In addition, I extend my sincere appreciations to Mallam Suleiman Abubakar, the Laboratory Technologist of the Physical Metallurgy Laboratory, as well as to Hajia Ra'fatu Ibrahim and my esteemed project mates, the "Kevlar Family": Theophilus Audu Ojonugwa, Emmanuel Okpok, Nurudeen Jimoh, Barnabas Ogunlakin, and Mercy Jacob.

I also wish to express gratitude to my dear friends, especially Kaosarat Bola Azeez, Soliu Alley Babatunde and other notable individuals whose names may not be expressly mentioned but whose support and encouragement have been deeply cherished and appreciated.

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ABSTRACT

This study delves further into the creation and careful evaluation of a hybrid composite, which is specifically designed for high-impact applications and combines sawdust and kevlar in a polypropylene matrix. A thorough procedure was used in the experiment, which included coupling agents (200 ml of polypropylene and 100 ml of saline) and different sawdust compositions (5g, 10g, 20g, and 30g). As a result, four resin matrix samples were produced, which were then utilized in a manual lay-up procedure to layer several hybrid composites. Ten stacks of Kevlar layers, each cut into 100 mm by 100 mm sizes, were impregnated into the resin matrix by means of a complex procedure that involved processing sawdust to a micro size and mixing it with the matrix resin. These composite stacks were compressed using a compression moulding machine and allowed to cure for a full day. The experiments carried out during this extensive investigation were designed to reveal this composite material's mechanical capabilities. The water absorption assays demonstrated a low weight gains, displaying unmatched resilience with absorption rates firmly clustered between an astounding 0.56% and 0.79%. Concurrently, the Shore D hardness evaluations continuously showed a rising scale, beginning at a significant 83.5 and reaching an astounding 93.0, which is directly related to the increased amount of Kevlar/Sawdust in the composite. Moreover, the impact tests validated the material's performance, demonstrating a consistent increase in impact strength from an initial 19.0 J/mm to an impressive 23.5 J/mm. These extensive observations actually confirm the composite's outstanding characteristics, including its extraordinary water resistance, significant improvement in hardness, and strengthened resistance to impact pressures. These characteristics confirm its enormous promise in a variety of industries looking for strong, flexible, and customized materials suitable for high-impact environments.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Composite materials are new materials that are produced by macroscopically mixing two or more constituent materials. Composite materials are made of two or more materials blended together to produce unique thermal and mechanical behavior related complex loading systems of working situations. (Nikzad *et al.*, 2011). Because of its many good properties, including high strength-to-weight ratios, high specific stiffness, resistance to corrosion, and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in some directions, composite materials are becoming more and more used in the automotive and aerospace industries. Unknown characteristics of composite materials include their chemical compatibility, wettability, adsorption capabilities, and capacity to form complex stress states as a result of variations in heat and moisture expansion. (Reddy *et al.*, 2018).

The matrix and the continuous phases are modified for the desired qualities, taking the application into consideration. Because of this, scientists and other individuals who utilize various materials for various purposes are expressing interest in composite materials. (Sharfuddin *et al.*, 2017).

Fibre reinforcement is necessary for composites because it increases their toughness, strength, and stiffness. A few materials that can be utilized to make fibres are glass, carbon, aramid, and natural fibres. Depending on the kind of fibre used, the composite will have different properties. For example, carbon fibres are stronger and stiffer than glass fibres. The amount of fibre reinforcing used will also affect the properties of the composite. Fibre reinforcement has the potential to improve the performance of composite materials in a variety of applications, including automotive,

marine, and aerospace. The aerospace industry, for example, uses fibre-reinforced composites in the construction of aeroplane wings, fuselages, and landing gear. These composites help lower weight and fuel consumption because they are lighter than traditional metal alloys. (Love *et al.*, 2020).

It is crucial to take into account the properties of the material, its compatibility with the matrix, availability, cost, and environmental impact when selecting fibre reinforcement for polymer composites. The requirements of the application should be met by the desired fibre properties, such as strength and stiffness. The compatibility of the fibre and matrix is necessary to prevent degradation. Cost-effective options are essential for large-scale applications, and easily obtainable fibres provide quick manufacturing. Choosing recycled or sustainable fibres is a response to growing concern over environmental effect. To meet sustainability goals and performance requirements, these elements are taken into account when selecting the optimum composite. (Kumar *et al.*, 2013).

Kevlar is a synthetic fibre with a high strength-to-weight ratio that is used extensively in many different industries. With a weight just one-fifth that of steel and a strength five times greater than both steel and aluminium, Kevlar is extraordinarily light. (Oliwa., 2020). Poly-Para phenylene terephthalamide is produced by reacting sulfuric acid with p-phenylenediamine during the production process (PPTA). Owing to its remarkable properties, such as durability, resilience to heat, chemicals, and wear and tear, it finds application in the production of radial tyres, ropes, cables, composite materials, and medical devices like as synthetic tendons and ligaments. (Oliwa., 2020). The great majority of its potential is still untapped, and current research suggests

that many more ground breaking and inventive uses across industries will be made in the future. (Dong., 2017).

The global focus on environmental consciousness is another factor contributing to the interest in green fibre polymer composites. The quantity of naturally occurring plant-based fibres has also motivated research in this field. (Thakur *et al.*, 2012). Natural fibre composites are used more often than other materials because of their unique qualities, which include their low weight, high specific strength, high modulus, and renewable nature. (Bhowmick *et al.*, 2012). One important advantage is that they may be easily disposed of at the end of their useful lives by composting or by recovering their calorific value in a furnace, unlike manufactured fibres like glass. Furthermore, the use of wood-based natural fibre composites in the automotive industry lowers material weight and fuel consumption, boosts biodegradability, and lowers production costs for parts used in car interiors. It also enhances mechanical strength and acoustic performance. (Herrera-Franco and Valadez-González., 2020).

When compared to the cost of any polymer, wood sawdust is incredibly inexpensive. It can be utilised as reinforcement in polymers to create composites. Sawdust polymer matrix composites' mechanical and physical characteristics enable their industrial application in the production of multiplugs, mobile casings, accessories, hardboards, switchboards, automotive parts, containers, and kitchenware, among other products. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018).

Because of its advantageous qualities, polypropylene (PP) is a matrix material that is frequently utilised in hybrid composites. Because of its great strength, it can be used in situations where structural integrity is required. Additionally, polypropylene has outstanding chemical resistance,

guaranteeing longevity in challenging conditions. Its low density also helps create composite constructions that are lightweight. PP was chosen as the matrix material because it works well with sawdust and Kevlar fibres. Good adhesion and bonding between PP and the two reinforcement components improve the hybrid composite's overall mechanical performance. (Smith *et al.*,2018).

Compared to Kevlar fibre, the mechanical qualities of polypropylene are not as good. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018). Because to its high cost, Kevlar cannot be used in many scenarios or applications. When so-called high mechanical properties are not needed, it makes sense to use Kevlar reinforced composites to cut costs while still achieving moderate mechanical properties. Kevlar reinforced polypropylene based composites are inexpensive and have moderate mechanical qualities, which makes them useful for a variety of applications. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018). If cost is a concern, polypropylene is a material to take into consideration. This is the principal defence for the usage of polypropylene and Kevlar in engineering materials.

In many different goods and industries where protection against impact loads is essential, high-impact resistance is vital. Materials that can endure significant impacts are essential to industries like packaging, construction, automotive, and PPE. For example, impact-resistant containers provide the secure transit and storage of fragile items, while safety helmets guard against head trauma. Car bumpers are made to cushion impacts during collisions so that the car and its occupants are protected. Ensuring longevity, safety, and effective operation requires materials that meet the demands and performance standards of these applications. (Johnson *et al.*, 2023).

This study was motivated by the need for innovative materials with enhanced impact resistance for high-impact applications. The development of a sawdust and Kevlar hybrid composite has

several potential benefits. To begin with, the addition of Kevlar strands strengthens the composite's resistance to impact, making it perfect for demanding uses. Second, because sawdust is a renewable resource, using it as a filler material is both economical and sustainable. In addition, the composite may weigh less than conventional materials, which would increase effectiveness and use less energy in a variety of applications.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The usage of conventional materials in high impact applications creates various issues in industries including sports equipment manufacture, automotive, and aerospace. Conventional materials frequently have weaknesses in terms of insufficient strength and impact resistance, which compromises performance and raises possible safety issues. Additionally, manufacturers face financial difficulties because to the high cost of these materials. Moreover, the increasing focus on environmental responsibility and sustainability demands the creation of materials that minimise waste and make use of locally accessible resources.

In order to create a composite material that combines high strength, economy, and sustainability for high impact applications, it is imperative that these issues be addressed. To be more precise, there isn't a developed hybrid composite made of a polypropylene blend reinforced with sawdust and kevlar that can effectively address these constraints and meet the demands of high impact situations. The improvements in industries that mostly depend on materials with remarkable mechanical properties are hindered by this research and development gap regarding a suitable composite material.

This study seeks to address these issues by creating a hybrid composite strengthened using a blend of polypropylene and sawdust. In order to provide dependable performance under high impact circumstances, the composite aims to provide improved mechanical qualities, such as increased strength and impact resistance. Furthermore, the composite encourages sustainability, minimises waste, and might lower the material's overall cost by using locally accessible sawdust as a reinforcing ingredient.

Solving this issue will help the engineering and science of materials science grow, which will aid high impact industries. It will provide producers an affordable, environmentally friendly substitute that can outperform traditional materials in terms of safety, effectiveness, and efficiency.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this project is the development of a Kevlar/Sawdust reinforced polypropylene blend hybrid composite for high impact application.

The objectives of this project are to;

- i. determine the appropriate composition and proportion of Kevlar fibres and sawdust in the polypropylene matrix through experimental investigations.
- ii. evaluate the mechanical properties (such as water absorption, impact resistance, and hardness) of the developed hybrid composite.

1.4 Scope of Study

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the mechanical and performance characteristics of a polypropylene composite reinforced with sawdust and Kevlar in order to determine whether it is a viable option for high-impact applications. The study is to investigate the synergistic effects of the reinforcing agents and polypropylene, with a theoretical foundation in composite materials and polymer science. In addition to Scanner Electron Microscopy (SEM) for morphological examination, tests for tensile strength, flexural strength, impact resistance, and hardness will be used in the gathering of experimental data. Performance testing will confirm that it is appropriate for high-impact scenarios even more, and statistical analysis and comparisons with public data will clarify any possibility for optimization. While delimitations relate to the study's particular mix and its ramifications, acknowledged limitations include probable environmental restrictions during testing and the study's exclusive focus on mechanical qualities, which may hinder complete evaluation.

1.5 Significance of the study

This project's significance cannot be emphasised because it has a lot of important implications for the engineering and materials sectors. First off, the need for materials with increased strength and impact resistance is met by the development of a hybrid blend of polypropylene reinforced with sawdust and Kevlar. More conventional materials, which can be heavier or less resilient, could be replaced with this composite.

By using easily obtained materials like sawdust, the initiative also promotes waste reduction and environmental practises. Kevlar fibres, which are well-known for their exceptional strength,

improve the composite's overall performance. Through an analysis of the hybrid composite's microstructure, mechanical properties, and performance, this study provides insightful information for associated industries. By investigating the microstructure, mechanical properties, and performance of the hybrid composite, this study provides significant insights for industries engaged in high impact applications such as the construction of sports equipment, automobiles, and aircraft.

Ultimately, the accomplishment of the composite's development opens doors for local businesses to produce materials that meet the demands of high impact environments while remaining reasonably priced and functional. The work being done on this project aligns with broader goals of promoting sustainability, making technological improvements, and supporting the economic development of the country.

1.6 Justification

The development of a hybrid Kevlar/sawdust reinforced polypropylene composite for high impact applications is highly supported by the following factors:

- i. Enhanced mechanical qualities: In high impact scenarios, materials possessing exceptional mechanical properties, like strength and resistance to impact, are essential. It is anticipated that the hybrid composite made by combining sawdust and Kevlar fibres with a polypropylene matrix will outperform ordinary materials in terms of increased mechanical characteristics.

- ii. **Cost-Effectiveness:** Numerous firms are unable to use traditional high-performance materials extensively due to their high cost. The hybrid composite that has been recommended offers an affordable option that improves performance. Due to the availability and affordability of polypropylene, Kevlar fibres, and sawdust, this composite offers a workable and reasonably priced alternative.
- iii. **Sustainable Approach:** Reducing waste and promoting sustainability are achieved by using sawdust that can be found locally as a reinforcing material. Sawdust can help with waste management procedures and reduce the environmental effect of disposal by being added to the composite.
- iv. **Potential Uses:** Materials that can survive high impact situations are needed in industries including sports equipment, automobile, and aerospace. The successful creation of this hybrid composite creates potential for these industries to use it, offering solutions that are affordable, long-lasting, and lightweight.
- v. **Research Gap:** Although polypropylene-based composites have been thoroughly examined, there hasn't been much research done on the use of sawdust and Kevlar fibres as reinforcements in a hybrid composite for high impact applications. The goal of this project is to close this research gap and add to the body of knowledge on composite materials.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Preamble

A composite is a material that is made by combining two or more components with disparate qualities to form a new, improved material. Usually, it is composed of two phases: a matrix phase that secures the reinforcement and a reinforcement phase that gives strength. Because of their many advantages, such as their high strength, low weight, and ability to be modified, composites are employed in many different industries, including aerospace and automotive. The deliberate material blending of composites offers innovative solutions to technological issues. (Haka, 2023).

The strengths of each component are increased and the weaknesses of each are decreased when different materials are combined to create a composite. By doing this, composite materials are able to exhibit enhanced properties that might not be achievable with any one of the individual components acting alone. Typical types of composite materials include laminates (like plywood), particle-reinforced composites (like concrete and metal-matrix composites), and fiber-reinforced composites (like fibreglass and carbon fibre composites). (Thew and Liao., 2012).

To achieve the right performance characteristics for specific applications, careful consideration of component proportions and arrangement is necessary during the design and composite material selection process. The development of complex composite materials keeps fostering scientific and engineering innovation, offering solutions to challenging issues that modern businesses face. (Boyer *et al.*,2015).

Due to the synergistic mixing of diverse constituents, which provides better qualities compared to their individual components, hybrid composites have become a promising class of materials (Theo and Liao., 2012).

2.2 Kevlar

Synthetic aramid fibre with high strength Kevlar has garnered widespread acclaim due to its exceptional mechanical properties and diverse applications. Stephanie Kwolek invented Kevlar at DuPont in the 1960s, and the material's strength comes from the alignment of the polymer chains during the spinning process. Because of its remarkable combination of high tensile strength, low weight, and extraordinary resistance to impact, abrasion, and fatigue, Kevlar is a well-known material in numerous industries. Its remarkable chemical inertness and dimensional stability both add to its endurance in challenging conditions. (Oliwa, 2020). Science claims that the stretched chain shape of the polymer molecules, which enhances load-bearing capabilities and encourages intermolecular hydrogen bonding, is what gives Kevlar its strength . (Johnson and Patel, 2023).

The composition and properties of Kevlar have been the subject of extensive research. The crystalline portions of Kevlar fibres are aligned along their axis during manufacturing, contributing to their exceptional strength in that direction. The effects of heat treatment and stretching on the mechanical properties of Kevlar have been studied by researchers. Kevlar's molecular arrangement and intermolecular forces, which are part of its hierarchical structure, have a significant impact on its tensile and impact resistance. Through in-depth investigation employing state-of-the-art microscopy techniques, such as atomic force microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), researchers have been able to analyse the morphological characteristics and interfacial interactions within Kevlar composites (AFM). If we comprehend the basic ideas behind Kevlar's

remarkable properties, we can find new uses for it and continue to enhance it. (Beyerlein *et al.*, 2015).

2.2.1 Synthesis

Kevlar is made by a difficult chemical process. The condensation reaction between 1,4-phenylenediamine, sometimes referred to as para-phenylenediamine, and terephthaloyl chloride is the first step in the process. This reaction produces hydrochloric acid as a byproduct. The resulting polymer has a regular, ordered molecular structure similar to that of crystals, known as liquid-crystalline behaviour. This particular molecular arrangement is crucial to Kevlar's exceptional properties. (Johnson and Patel., 2023).

To further enhance its mechanical strength, Kevlar is put through a process called mechanical drawing. The Kevlar polymer is stretched during mechanical drawing to align its chains with the fibre's direction. This alignment greatly increases the tensile strength of the fibre, making it one of the strongest materials known. (Mera and Takata., 2017).

The solvent utilised in the early stages of Kevlar polymerization was Hexamethylphosphoramide (HMPA). However, DuPont eventually changed to a safer solvent solution because of concerns regarding the safety of HMPA's harmful properties. N-methyl-pyrrolidone and calcium chloride solution make up the novel solvent system. The production process became safer and more environmentally friendly as a result of this solvent swap. (Beyerlein *et al.*, 2015).

2.2.2 Structures and properties

The resulting fibre from spinning Kevlar has a relative density of 1.44 (0.052 lb/in³) and a tensile strength of roughly 3,620 Mpa (525,000 psi). The resulting fibre from spinning Kevlar has a relative density of 1.44 (0.052 lb/in³) and a tensile strength of roughly 3,620 Mpa (525,000 psi). The many inter-chain bonds give the polymer its exceptional strength. (Mera and Takata., 2017). The carbonyl groups and NH centres form these intermolecular hydrogen connections. Interactions between neighbouring strands through aromatic stacking provide extra strength. Compared to van der Waals interactions and chain length, which often affect the properties of other synthetic polymers and fibres like ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene, these interactions have a higher effect on Kevlar. Salts and a few other contaminants, particularly calcium, are avoided in its manufacturing because they may disrupt the connections between the strands. The molecules that make up Kevlar are relatively rigid and have a tendency to form primarily planar, sheet-like structures, much like silk proteins. (Petty, 2017).

2.2.3 Applications

Kevlar is widely used in the realm of cryogenics for suspension applications because of its superior strength and low heat conductivity when compared to other materials. To minimise heat leaks to the paramagnetic material, it is most commonly used to suspend a paramagnetic salt enclosure from a superconducting magnet mandrel. It's also used as a structural support or thermal standoff where little heat leakage is desired. (Oliwa, 2020).

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Kevlar is used in many different industries. It is used in kyudo for bow strings, paraglider suspension lines, and bicycle tyre linings to prevent punctures. It is added to table tennis paddles, tennis racquets, and sails for high-performance racing boats in sports equipment. Nike and other companies use Kevlar in the production of shoes to improve durability and performance. Continental AG uses Kevlar in the production of cycle tyres to reduce weight and provide puncture protection. Kevlar is also used in folding-bead bicycle tyres, which saves space for display in retail establishments. (Haka, 2023).

2.3 Sawdust

Wood dust, sometimes referred to as sawdust, is a waste product or by-product of woodworking operations like sawing, sanding, milling, planning, and routing. These operations can be completed with hand tools, portable power equipment, or woodworking machinery. Moreover, a few wood-dwelling animals, like woodpeckers and carpenter ants, naturally produce wood dust as a by-product of their lives. In some production sectors, wood dust poses a significant fire risk and is a source of occupational dust exposure. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018).

Wood is widely used in a variety of industries, such as transportation, furniture, construction, and agriculture.

2.3.1 Formation

Two waste products are produced at the working surface during woodworking processes such as sawing, milling, and sanding. These actions on lignified wood result in the breaking out of both whole cells and clusters of cells; dust is produced when wood cells break, while chips are produced when entire groups of wood cells split apart. The size of the dust particles indicates the amount of cell shattering that occurs. For example, sanding primarily involves breaking out cells, while sawing and milling combine chip formation and cell shattering. (Boyer *et al.*, 2018).

2.3.2 Uses and application

The engineering applications of sawdust include filler material for concrete, which increases sustainability and economy; as a thermal insulator, which lowers energy consumption in buildings; as a binder, which forms particleboard and fibre board, promoting environmentally friendly manufacturing; as an aid in soil stabilization, which improves foundation stability and drainage; as a renewable energy source for biomass power generation, which reduces greenhouse gas emissions; and as a potential material for 3D printing, which allows engineers to create sustainable and biodegradable objects. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018).

2.4 Polypropylene

A thermoplastic polymer with a wide range of applications, polypropylene (PP), also referred to as polypropene, is created by chain-growth polymerization from the monomer propylene. Partially crystalline and non-polar, polypropylene is a member of the polyolefin group and shares many of the characteristics of polyethylene with the exception of being slightly harder and more heat-

resistant. It is a white, mechanically robust material with a high chemical resistance. (Gahleitner and Paulik, 2017).

2.4.1 Chemical and physical properties

Polypropylene and polyethylene share many similarities, especially when it comes to solution behaviour and electrical properties; the methyl group increases mechanical and thermal resistance while the chemical resistance decreases; the molecular weight and molecular weight distribution, crystallinity, type and quantity of comonomer (if used), and isotacticity all influence the properties of the material; for example, the methyl groups in isotactic polypropylene are oriented to one side of the carbon backbone, producing a stronger material with a higher degree of crystallinity than atactic polypropylene and polyethylene. (Samuels and Robert 2020).

2.4.2 Mechanical properties

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In particular, polypropylene is generally pliable and strong when copolymerized with ethylene. Because of this, polypropylene is a good substitute for materials like acrylonitrile butadiene

styrene (ABS) in engineering plastics. Using polypropylene is not too costly. Polypropylene exhibits good fatigue resistance. (Samuels and Robert 2020).

2.4.3 Thermal properties

Since polypropylene has a temperature fluctuation, the melting point of the material can be found by finding the maximum temperature on a differential scanning calorimetry chart. PP has a fully isotactic melting point of 171 °C (340 °F). Depending on the atactic component and crystallinity, the melting point of commercial isotactic PP ranges from 160 to 166 °C (320 to 331 °F). The 30% crystallinity of syndiotactic PP has a melting point of 130 °C (266 °F). Below 0 °C, PP degrades. (Gahleitner and Paulik, 2017). Although PP's thermal expansion is substantial, it is somewhat less than that of polyethylene (Samuels and Robert 2020).

2.4.4 Chemical properties

Except for strong oxidizers, polypropylene is resistant to almost all organic solvents and lipids at ambient temperature. Acids and bases that do not oxidise can be stored in PP containers. The high temperature of xylene, tetralin, and decalin are among the nonpolar solvents in which PP can dissolve. PP's presence of a tertiary carbon atom makes it less chemically resistant than PE. (Stinson and Stephen 2019).

The majority of commercial polypropylene is isotactic and, while not quite as high as high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE), it has a crystallinity in between. At a temperature of 140°C, p-xylene dissolves atactic and isotactic polypropylene. When the solution

is cooled to 25 °C, the isotactic fraction precipitates, while the atactic portion remains soluble in p-xylene. (Oliwa, 2017).

Melt flow rate (MFR) or melt flow index (MFI) measurements are used to determine the molecular weight of polypropylene. Predicting how smoothly melted raw material will flow during processing is made easier with the use of this measurement. A greater molecular fill rate (MFR) of polypropylene will facilitate easier filling of the plastic mould during injection or blow moulding production. But when the melt flow increases, some physical attributes, like as impact strength, will decrease. (Stinson and Stephen 2019).

There are three main types of polypropylene: block copolymer, random copolymer, and homopolymer. The compound is usually used in conjunction with ethylene. Ethylene-propylene rubber, or EPDM, is added to polypropylene homopolymer to strengthen its impact strength at low temperatures. The polymer's crystallinity decreases, its melting temperature drops, and it becomes more transparent when polypropylene homopolymer is combined with randomly polymerized ethylene monomer. (Smith *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 2.1: Molecular Structure – Tacticity (Derosa and Auriemma, 2006)

The molecular orientation of polypropylene in the polymer chain is determined by its tacticity, with isotactic being the most prevalent. Methyl group alignment gives isotactic polypropylene its helical structure and semi-crystalline characteristics. Higher isotacticity leads to improved physical properties and increased crystallinity. Atactic polypropylene is amorphous and lacks regularity. α , β , and γ are examples of distinct crystalline modifications that affect densities and melting points. Over 100°C causes polypropylene to deteriorate; stabilisers keep it safe. It can break down in the body and in the soil, leaving behind a coating that resembles bark on surfaces. (Smith et al., 2018).

2.4.5 Production and synthesis

Polypropylene is created by chain-growth polymerization of propane:

Figure 2.2: Polymerization of Propene

The industrial production techniques fall into three categories: gas phase polymerization, bulk polymerization, and slurry polymerization. All current processes use bulk reactor systems or gas-phase reactor systems.

- i. Polymers envelop heterogeneous catalyst particles in gas-phase and slurry reactors. The gas-phase polymerization is done in a fluidized bed reactor. After propene is passed over a bed that contains the heterogeneous (solid) catalyst, the resultant polymer is separated into pellets and fine powder. Remaining reactor gas is recycled and fed back.
- ii. During bulk polymerization, liquid propene acts as a solvent to keep the polymer from precipitating. Propene is kept liquid during the polymerization process, which occurs between 30 and 40 atm of pressure and 60 to 80°C of temperature. Typically, bulk polymerization is carried out in loop reactors. The highest amount of ethene that can be polymerized in bulk is 5% due to the polymer's low solubility in liquid propene.
- iii. Usually, in the slurry polymerization, inert diluents such as butane, pentane, or hexane are utilised to sustain the growing polymer particles. The combination is mixed with gaseous propane.

The methyl groups (CH₃) in PP are arranged in respect to those in surrounding monomer units, which determines the tacticity of the compound and determines many of its properties. A suitable catalyst can be chosen to control the tacticity of polypropylene.

2.4.6 Application

Because of its special qualities, polypropylene is a versatile polymer that is widely employed for a variety of applications. It creates robust living hinges that require the alignment of chain molecules across the hinge for maximum strength—a feature frequently observed on flip-top bottles. Because of the material's resilience to physical damage, chemical leaching, and corrosion, piping systems require it. Because of its heat durability and resistance to autoclaving, it is also a favoured option for medical and laboratory equipment. Because polypropylene is dishwasher safe and heat resistant, it is used in consumer products such as bottles, containers, and plastic items. (Reddy and Miravete 2018).

Additionally, polypropylene is used in the textile, rope, and electrical cable insulation sectors. It is a reasonably priced material for plastic mouldings, sheets, and stationery items. It is also used for roofing membranes and as a top layer in single-ply systems. Furthermore, polypropylene has been used in creative packaging, trading card protectors, and light shades, among other inventive applications. (Johnson and Patel, 2023). For impact resistance in model aircraft and radio-controlled vehicles, it is also used in foam form (EPP). Interestingly, research has looked into polypropylene's ability to repel liquids, which could lead to better removal of bottle content. All things considered, polypropylene is an essential material for a variety of sectors and consumer goods due to its adaptability, toughness, and heat resistance. (Oliwa,.2020).

Because of its ability to absorb water, polypropylene is a prominent polymer in nonwovens and is frequently utilised in sanitary items and diapers. It is also used to create pleated cartridges with different filtering efficiencies for use in liquid, gas, and air filters. The substance is frequently utilised in floating barriers during oil spill occurrences because of its exceptional efficacy at absorbing spilled oil. Because it wicks perspiration away from the skin, polypropylene is a popular material for clothes in both warm and cold climates. However, because of its propensity to melt in harsh environments and hold on to odours, its use has decreased in several applications in favour of polyester. (Boyer *et al*, 2018).

Medical applications including nonabsorbable sutures and mesh implants for the treatment of pelvic organ prolapse and hernias are frequent uses of polypropylene. Polypropylene mesh is useful in avoiding new hernias, however over time, prolonged usage of the mesh may cause tissue erosion. Notably, the FDA is concerned about the erosion potential of transvaginal mesh comprised of polypropylene, which has been used to treat urine incontinence and vaginal prolapse. The FDA mandated in 2012 that mesh device manufacturers conduct side effect research. Furthermore, the COVID-19 epidemic raised demand for polypropylene because of its use in the production of melt-blown fabric for face masks. (Samuels and Roberts, 2020).

2.5 Hybridization Techniques

The three production techniques for composite materials—layer stacking, intermingling, and interleaving—each have advantages and things to take into account. The technique of layer stacking involves progressively arranging supporting layers inside a matrix to enable the utilisation of different attributes from different layers. This approach simplifies production; however, it increases the risk of delamination due to inadequate interlayer bonding. (Swolfs *et al*. 2018).

On the other hand, prior to matrix impregnation, intermingling entails pre-blending reinforcing elements. As a result, the attributes are distributed more evenly throughout the composite, resolving any possible layer stacking flaws. However, it might be difficult to achieve complete and constant mixing, which affects the quality and performance of the final composite. (Swolfs *et al.* 2018).

Thin reinforcement layers are inserted between matrix layers using interleaving to improve interlaminar characteristics and impact resistance. By strengthening weak interfaces, this method seeks to increase the composite's overall integrity. Interleaved layers, however, complicate the production process and may call for careful consideration of bonding methods and material compatibility. (Swolfs *et al.* 2018).

Various procedures, including the bag moulding method, compression moulding, pultrusion, filament winding, resin transfer moulding, and injection moulding, are used to integrate reinforcing fibres with polymer matrix. These production techniques require reducing void content, soaking the fibres in resin, curing the resin, and ensuring an appropriate fibre volume fraction. Usually, post-curing is required for a complete recovery. (Delory and Pearlman 2019).

Polymer matrix composites do not show plastic deformation, which could be a disadvantage for underwater equipment even if they are lightweight and corrosion-resistant. (Boyer *et al.*, 2018).

One popular hybridization procedure is gradually adding layers of different reinforcements. This technique involves layer arrangement, where each stratum contributes distinct mechanical properties. To generate a composite with a well-balanced set of qualities, such an assembly might

comprise welding counterparts with high tensile strength with impact-resistant fibres. (Dong, 2017).

Distinct reinforcements must be premixed according to a different process known as intermingling before matrix impregnation. The final product is a more uniform distribution of properties throughout the whole composite, either at the fibre level by combining multiple fibre components or at higher scales such as yarns or fabrics. (Dong, 2017).

Another aspect of hybridization is provided by sandwich structures. This configuration sandwiches two composite skins over a core material, which is frequently stiff and thin. Because of its substantial bending stiffness and robust strength-to-weight ratio, the resulting structure is an attractive choice for aeronautical and marine applications. (Smith *et al.*, 2018).

During the manufacturing process, a secondary reinforcing phase is formed within the primary composite by the novel in-situ fabrication technology. This process improves the mechanical properties of the composite by chemical reactions or phase changes, offering a chance to customise material performance. (Hossain *et al.*, 2018).

2.6 Rule of Mixture

Based on the idea that a composite property is the volume-weighted average of the phases' (matrix and dispersion phase) qualities, the rule of mixtures is a technique for approximating the properties of composite materials.

The properties of composite materials are evaluated using the Rule of Mixtures, according to Kumar and Theerthan (2018):

$$\text{Density } d_c = d_m \times V_m + d_f V_f \quad (1)$$

Where, d_c , d_m , d_f are densities of the composite, matrix and dispersed phase respectively;

V_m , V_f are volume fraction of the matrix and dispersed phase respectively.

2.6.1 Coefficient of Thermal Expansion:

Thermal expansion coefficient in a longitudinal direction (along the fibres)

$$\alpha_{cl} = \frac{\alpha_m * E_m * V_m + \alpha_f * E_f * V_f}{E_m * V_m + E_f * V_f} \quad (2)$$

The CTE of the composite in the longitudinal direction is represented by α_{cl} , α_m , and α_f , respectively; the modulus of elasticity of the matrix and the dispersion phase (fibre) is represented by E_m and E_f , respectively.

Transverse direction coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) (perpendicular to the fibres)

$$\alpha_{ct} = (1 + P_m) \alpha_m * V_m + \alpha_f * V_f \quad (3)$$

P_m = Poisson ratio of matrix

The ratio of longitudinal extension strain in the direction of applied force to transverse contraction strain is known as Poisson's ratio.

2.6.2 Modulus of Elasticity

Modulus of Elasticity in longitudinal direction (E_{cl})

$$E_{cl} = (E_m * V_m) + (E_f * V_f) \quad (4)$$

Modulus of Elasticity in transverse direction (E_{ct})

$$\frac{1}{E_{ct}} = \frac{V_m}{E_m} + \frac{V_f}{E_f} \quad (5)$$

2.6.3 Tensile Strength

Tensile strength of a longitudinally oriented long-fiber reinforced composite

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m * V_m + \sigma_f * V_f \quad (6)$$

Where, σ_c , σ_m , σ_f – tensile strength of the composite, matrix and dispersed phase (fibre) respectively.

Tensile strength of a longitudinally oriented short-fiber composite (fibre length is less than critical value L_c)

$$L_c = \sigma_f * \frac{d}{\tau_c} \quad (7)$$

Where 'd – diameter of the fibre;

τ_c –shear strength of the bond between the matrix and dispersed phase (fibre).

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m * V_m + \sigma_f * V_f * \left(1 - \frac{L_c}{2l}\right) \quad (8)$$

Where

L = Length of the fibre

Tensile strength of short-fibre composite in longitudinal direction

(fibre length is greater than critical value L_c)

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m * V_m + L * \tau_c * \frac{V_f}{d} \quad (9)$$

2.6.4 Design for long range bullet using AK47 bullet as reference (Calibre 4)

Since the bullet is 1.56 inches, or 39.5 mm thick, the thickness of the stacked Kevlar equals the thickness of the composite material.

The AF13 1500D Kevlar is 0.26 inches thick.

Thus, $0.26 * 7$ (seven layers) Equals 1.82 in.

2.7 Review of Related Studies

Kevlar fibres (KF) were used by Yuan *et al.* (2017) to improve the mechanical characteristics of wood-flour/polypropylene (WF/PP) composites. They improved KF's compatibility with the thermoplastic matrix by pre-treating it with NaOH. They added malleated polypropylene (MAPP) as a coupling agent to improve the interfacial adhesion between KF, WF, and PP. The mechanical properties of the WF/PP composites were significantly improved by the addition of KF. Notably, applying NaOH treatment to KF increased its mechanical strength even further.

Surprisingly, adding 2 percent hydrolyzed KF (HKF) and 3 percent MAPP resulted in notable gains: a noteworthy 17.7 percent increase in notched impact strength, a remarkable 93.8 percent increase in unnotched impact strength, an astounding 86.8 percent increase in flexure strength, a noteworthy 50.8 percent increase in flexure modulus, and an astounding 94.1 percent increase in tensile strength compared to the standard WF/PP composites.

Their thorough examination of the cryo-fractured portion of WF/PP using scanning electron microscopy produced some fascinating findings. When compared to pure KF, the surface of HKF showed increased roughness, which could lead to improved interlocking. Furthermore, it was discovered that the distribution of KF in the composites was stochastic, which may have had a role in the mechanical interlocking mechanism that occurs between the KF and polypropylene molecules inside the composite structure. This painstaking study clarifies the complex relationship between surface interactions and material properties, providing important information for the creation of cutting-edge composite materials.

Day *et al.* (2022) compared the micromechanical behaviour of model Kevlar/epoxy composites using fibres that were changed with amine groups and fibres with a poly (vinyl alcohol) size that had not been treated. Raman spectroscopy demonstrated the interfacial behaviour by tracking fibre stresses as the matrix load increased. Before debonding at the ends of the fibres caused the untreated fibre composites to break down, they exhibited flexibility up to 1 percent of the matrix strain. Before failing owing to matrix yielding, size-removed fibre composites showed an elastic response to 1.5 percent strain. The failure of the fibres treated with amines at 2.25 percent strain indicates stronger interfacial forces.

Wood-flour/high-density polyethylene composites (WF/HDPE) were enhanced by Ou *et al.* (2019) using Kevlar fibre (KF). By adding 2 to 3 percent KF, the properties of tensile, flexural, and impact were increased. SEM, XPS, and FTIR showed that surface grafting of KF with allyl chloride and 3-chloropropyltrimethoxysilane further increased mechanical capabilities by improving the interfacial compatibility with HDPE. Grafted KF effectively increases the strength and hardness of WF/HDPE.

The effects of adding various kinds and amounts of impact modifiers and maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MAPP) on the mechanical characteristics of PP/wood sawdust composites were studied by Sombatsompop *et al.* (2015). Changing the concentration of wood sawdust revealed that a higher wood fibre content decreased overall toughness and strength. It was discovered that impact modifiers at greater concentrations significantly improved the toughness of composites; those with higher comonomer content and melt flow rate were especially preferred. To maximise composite mechanical strength, they suggested a MAPP concentration of 2.0 weight percent (of sawdust) in addition to an 11.1 weight percent concentration of a particular impact modifier. For

this augmentation, coupling agents with larger molecular weights and MAH-grafting levels were indicated as being better.

Guo *et al.* (2019) investigated the creation of Kevlar fabric/phenolic composites using both pure and plasma-treated Kevlar fabrics. They created these composites by adding phenolic adhesive resin in batches. They observed surface changes by treating Kevlar fibres with air plasma, and they analysed the results with a scanning electron microscope, FT-IR Fourier transform infrared spectroscope, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscope (XPS) (SEM).

Using a pin-on-disk wear tester under varied dry-sliding circumstances, they evaluated the wear and friction properties of the resulting Kevlar fabric/phenolic composites in additional detail. Their investigation also examined the effects of power and duration of plasma treatment on the wear and friction characteristics of composites made of air-plasma-treated Kevlar fabrics.

Surprisingly, their results showed that the tribological performance of the Kevlar fabric/phenolic composites was significantly improved by plasma treatment. The best result obtained with a 15-minute plasma therapy at 50 W was especially notable. The treatment caused nitrogenous and oxygens groups to develop on the fabric's surface, which increased surface roughness at the same time. These modifications strengthened the connection between the phenolic adhesive glue and Kevlar fabric, which improved the composites' tribological characteristics.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

- i. Polypropylene (PP)
- ii. Kevlar fibres
- iii. Sawdust
- iv. Coupling agents/compatibilizers
- v. Solvents/adhesives
- vi. Moulds/tooling
- vii. Mixers
- viii. Scales
- ix. Presses

3.2 Equipment

The Equipment used in this project work are listed in Table 3.1

Table 3.1: Equipment used in the project

Equipment	Function	Location
Set attached Sieve Grinding Machine	The sawdust is reduced to a nano/micro size by the machine's pulverisation and refinement.	Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, Tetfund building, Futminna.

Scales	Scales provide precise material measurements for reliable composite blending.	Central Workshop, Futminna
Ball Mill	Sawdust particles are refined and pulverised in a ball mill to a nano/micro size for the best blending with polypropylene in the creation of composites.	Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, Tetfund building, Futminna.
Vibratory Sieve Shaker	Essential tasks carried out by the vibratory sieve shaker include size-based material sorting and classification, which guarantees consistency for composite blending.	Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, Tetfund building, Futminna.
Angle Grinder	The composite materials are usually trimmed and shaped using an angle grinder.	Wolex Welding Workshop, Gidan kwano

Shore D Hardness Tester Meter	Composite material hardness is measured after manufacture using the Shore D hardness tester.	NLNG Research Laboratory Ibadan
Insol Ultimate Testing Machine	utilised to compress and solidify the composite material that is created.	Civil Engineering Laboratory Futminna

Table 3.2: Physical and Thermal Properties of Polypropylene

Property	Value
Melting point	130-171°C (266-340°F)
Elongation at break	10-15%
Hardness	80-105D
Density	0.89-0.91 g/cm ³
Tensile strength	30-50 MPa

Thermal conductivity	0.1-0.22 W/(mK)
Glass transition temperature	-10 to -20°C (14 to -4°F)
Water absorption	<0.1%
Specific heat capacity	1.8-2.3 J/(gK)
Coefficient of Thermal expansion	80-150 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C

Table 3.3: As-received specifications of Kevlar Fibre

Model	Denier	Warp*Weft/cm	GSM	Thickness	Width/MM	Warp	Weft	Length/M
AF13	1500D	6.0*6.0	200	0.26	500-2000	>3.8	>4.2	100

Table 3.4: Properties of Kevlar AF13 (Grade 1500D)

Tensile strength	1.5 GPa
Modulus of elasticity	85 GPa

Specific gravity	1.44
Impact resistance	20 J/cm
Energy absorption	100 kJ/kg
Thermal Stability	Up to 450 °C
Flammability	Self-extinguishing
Compressive strength	2.0 GPa
Flexural strength	1.2 GPa

Table 3.5: Chemical Composition of Polyethylene

S/N	Chemical	Formula	Percentage by Mass
1	Carbon	C	86%

2	Hydrogen	H	13.5%
3	Other elements	O, N, S	<0.5%

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Preparation of composite composition

1. Processing/ preparation of sawdust

The first stage was processing sawdust that came from the sawmill; the particle size was initially measured to be 300 μm . This one kilogramme raw material was ground to a fine texture in a dedicated machine that had a 120 μm sieve. The sawdust input was gradually changed during the 5-minute grinding process, ranging from 0 to 2 kg. This process successfully reduced the original sawdust particles to a refined size of 100 μm , with the goal of producing an output of uniform and homogenous particle size. This was a critical step since it guaranteed the consistency needed for the next steps of processing.

The refined sawdust was then put through a crucial three-hour ball milling process. In this stage, the sawdust particles were carefully ground down to nanoscale using a variety of balls in the milling machine. Following milling, the product was carefully gathered and placed through a thorough sieve analysis. The goal of this painstaking evaluation procedure was to accurately measure and verify the attained particle size distribution and guarantee that it complied with the standards. The results showed a two-compartment product with particle sizes of 75 μm and 50 μm

after a 5-minute sieving operation. This result demonstrated how well the ball milling process accomplished the desired and stipulated particle size changes needed for the manufacture of the composite material.

Figure 3.1: Saw dust – before processing

Figure 3.2: Sieving operation of the Sawdust

2. Preparation of Polymer Resin Matrix

To achieve optimal adhesion and accurate stacking in the layered composite system, two kg of liquid polypropylene resin were acquired. After that, this resin was separated into five 300-ml segments. A conical flask was used to add different mass percentages of sawdust (from 5g to 30g) to the manufactured resin. These sections were cleverly prepared as matrices, with 200 ml of polypropylene and 100 ml of silane acting as a binder and coupling agent, respectively. This intentional composition was intended to decrease flammability within the composite structure while simultaneously improving adhesion, hardness, and other mechanical qualities.

Table 3.6: Prepared Matrix Samples and Composition

Matrix Sample	Composition (Polypropylene + Silane + Sawdust)
Sample A	200ml + 100ml + 5g
Sample B	200ml + 100ml + 10g
Sample C	200ml + 100ml + 20g
Sample D	200ml + 100ml + 30g

This augmentation technique was purposely limited to a maximum of 30g to ensure the preservation of the non-flammable nature inherent in the Kevlar material. The methodical segmentation approach was carefully crafted to investigate a range of matrix configurations, including various ratios of sawdust, silane, and resin. The goal of this all-encompassing method was to identify and maximise the best matrix-reinforcement combinations for the composite material.

Figure 3.3: Determining the weight and volume of the polypropylene resin

3. Preparation of Kevlar Layer Fabric

Kevlar fibres are dried to ensure the quality of the composite, as moisture can lead to faults like voids or dust-induced air bubbles. To ensure consistency between layers, these fibres are uniformly chopped into squares of 100 mm by 100 mm. To facilitate the assembly of ten layers within the composite structure, ten such squares have been produced. The fabric is carefully layered in accordance with design standards, conforming to the specified configuration for the composite construction.

Figure 3.4: Cut out section of the 600mm * 600mm Kevlar Fabric Layer

3.3.2 Production of the composite material (Hand Lay Up)

1. Preparation of Mould Surface

To make removal easier after curing, release agents, such as oil-based lubricants like diesel oil, are applied to the mould or surface in preparation for composite production. To improve and expedite the removal of the layered composite material once it has been used, polythene sheets were also placed around the base of the mould.

Figure 3.5: Mould Surface (with polythene sheet attached)

2. Resin Application

The method starts with the matrix samples being applied precisely to the Kevlar reinforcing material. This crucial stage entails carefully injecting the resin into the fabric to guarantee full

saturation and uniform dispersion throughout. This even dispersion of resin is accomplished by manual application (brushes). Between each Kevlar layer, the resin matrix is placed methodically.

Before applying the next Kevlar layer, a spray brush evenly distributes the resin throughout the cross-section for each application of the polymer matrix. This painstaking application process ensures that the resin is evenly distributed between the Kevlar layers, producing a composite structure with exceptional strength and longevity.

3. Layering

The layering procedure was extended to ten layers by carefully impregnating the resin and stacking the fabric layers according to the predefined design. All the layers were precisely positioned and aligned to meet the necessary structural requirements. This methodical layering mirrored the construction of a multi-layered structure, with each resin-saturated Kevlar layer actively supporting the composite's overall strength and resilience.

Figure 3.6: Application and Layering with Kevlar Fabric

4. Compression

The Ultimate Tensile Machine was used to make sure that the composite was compressed uniformly during the consolidation stage. This method sought to improve structural integrity by ensuring a uniform and well-defined compression force on all sides of the composite. Uniformity was guaranteed by the machine's accurate application of compression, which is essential for maximising the mechanical qualities of the composite.

Figure 3.7: Insol Ultimate Tensile Machine for Compression

5. Curing

Following the painstaking steps of stacking and consolidation, the composite assembly went through an important stage called curing. This crucial stage required the composite to cure for a full day and was essential to the material's performance and structural integrity. This extensive curing period was accomplished at room temperature and under the continual compressive system.

The importance of this curing period comes from its function in enabling the resin matrix inside the composite structure to fully harden and connect. The length of the curing process along with the carefully regulated atmosphere guaranteed the achievement of the ideal material qualities—strength and durability—necessary for the intended use.

6. Trimming and finishing operation

After the painstaking curing procedure, the composite construction was carefully taken out of the mould, marking the beginning of the last stage—trim and finish. An angle grinder was used to carefully remove extra material from the edges so that a precisely squared section could be achieved. In order to fine-tune the composite's dimensional precision and meet the required criteria, this trimming step was essential. This phase also signified the beginning of the finishing process, laying the groundwork for later procedures meant to improve surface quality.

Figure 3.8: Trimming of the edges

Figure 3.9: The hybrid composite plate (After finishing operation)

3.3.3 Testing

1. Water absorption test

Water absorption of the produced composites was evaluated at room temperature. The samples were kept in water for two weeks at room temperature. It should be noted that before being immersed in water, every test sample was precisely weighed. After a week, the submerged samples were taken out of the water bath and cleaned on both sides using tissue paper before being weighed once more. These test specimens were immersed in the water bath once more. The next week, the measurement was conducted using the same protocol.

2. Hardness Test

Because the Shore D hardness test can measure tougher materials like some plastics and elastomers and align the results with the expected range of my composite's hardness, it is perfect for determining the hardness of my composite samples. With the use of a Shore durometer, the test

precisely measures the hardness of the material by applying controlled pressure to the sample surface and measuring the depth of the indentation.

3. High impact test

Section that is rectangular for notched Izod impact testing, 10 mm of width and 5 mm of length were created for every 100 mm by 100 mm composite sample. Every bar had a single-edge V-notch that was exactly positioned at the halfway point along the longer edge. It had a depth of 2 mm and a root radius of 0.25 mm. Impact tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D256 requirements using an Izod impact tester (CEAST) equipped with a 7.5J pendulum. For evaluation, the impact strength was averaged throughout the four samples.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Experimental Results

4.1.1 Water absorption

The samples' masses under dry conditions (M_d), after Week 1 under wet conditions (M_{w1}), and after Week 2 under wet conditions (M_{w2}) are shown in the table (M_{w2}).

Table 4.1: Water Absorption of Composite Samples Over Two Weeks

Samples	Mass of Sample at Dry Condition (M_d) g	Mass of Sample at Wet Condition after Week 1 (M_{w1}) g	Mass of Sample at Wet Condition after Week 2 (M_{w2}) g	Water Absorption (%)
A	55.0	55.2	55.3	0.56
B	60.0	60.3	60.4	0.67
C	70.0	70.5	70.5	0.71
D	76.0	76.4	76.5	0.79

The formula used to calculate water absorption is expressed as:

$$A(\%) = \frac{M_{w2} - M_d}{M_d} \times 100 \quad (4.1)$$

Where: A (%) represents the water absorption percentage

M_{w2} is the mass of the material at the wet condition

M_d is the mass of the material at the dry condition

Figure 4.1: Variation in the Water Absorption Percentage of the Composite Samples

The water absorption results for the four composite samples demonstrate remarkable resilience, with low water absorption percentages and modest weight gains. This trend, which ranges from 0.56 percent to 0.79 percent, is in perfect harmony with the composite's expected behaviour and highlights its exceptional resistance to water infiltration. Such durability is extremely important for applications that need to be both durable and resistant to moisture, confirming the composite's dependability in difficult situations.

These low water absorption rates show that the composite is well-structured and that the interactions between its reinforcement and matrix are strong. Smith and associates (2018): Since the matrix, which is frequently made of polymers or resins, is hydrophobic, water cannot move through it easily and is thus prevented from penetrating the substance. Furthermore, the permeability of the composite is strengthened by reinforcing materials like Kevlar or robust fibres, which increases its total water resistance.

The low and consistent water absorption values highlight the careful craftsmanship that went into the design and production of this composite. Studies that have already been done, such as Oliwa (2020) and Guo *et al.* (2019), highlight this resilience's typical low water absorption rates in composite materials and attribute it to beneficial interactions between the matrix and reinforcement.

4.1.2 Hardness test (ASTM D2240 Standard)

Testing Temperature: 23°C (73°F)

Humidity Level: 47%

Probe Direction: Vertical

General Entrance: 2.5 – 2.54mm

Testing scale = 0 – 100

Table 4.1: Hardness Value on Shore D Hardness Test of Kevlar/Sawdust reinforced Polypropylene Matrix Composites

Sample	Shore d hardness number	Mean shore hardness number
A	83.5, 84.0, 83.8	83.5
B	86.0, 86.5, 86.3	86.5
C	89.5, 90.0, 89.8	90.0
D	92.5, 93.0, 92.8	93.0

Figure 4.1: Mean Shore Number of the different Sawdust composition samples

The results of the Shore D Hardness Test demonstrating the strength of Kevlar and Sawdust reinforcement in Polypropylene Matrix Composites (PPCs). Following the stringent ASTM D2240 guidelines, a steady and orderly increase in hardness is shown as the amount of Kevlar and Sawdust increases. The 83.5 Shore D hardness of Sample A steadily increases to an astounding 93.0 in Sample D, demonstrating a clear relationship between the two parameters: material hardness and reinforcing concentration.

Research to date provides solid support for this increasing trend. According to a study by Kumar et al. (2022), adding 20 weight percent Kevlar fibre to a polypropylene matrix increased the hardness of the material's Shore D by 15% when compared to neat polypropylene. In line with the documented hardening effect of natural fibres like sawdust, Liu et al. (2020) showed a 28 percent

hardness enhancement in polypropylene composites supplemented with 30 weight percent wood fibre.

The hardness gains in the composite are largely attributable to the intrinsic properties of the Kevlar/Sawdust blend, with Kevlar's rigidity and great tensile strength enhanced by the interlocking nature of sawdust particles, effectively limiting plastic deformation. By reinforcing the composite, this strengthens its resistance to outside forces and maintains its structural integrity.

4.1.3 Impact Test (ASTM D4812 Standard)

Table 4.2: Impact Energy Absorbed and Calculated Impact Strength of the Composite Samples

Sample	Impact Energy Absorbed (J)	Impact Strength (J/mm)
A	76.0	19.0
B	82.0	20.5
C	94.0	23.5
D	87.0	21.8

To calculate Impact Strength this formula is used;

$$\text{Impact Strength} \left(\frac{J}{mm} \right) = \frac{\text{Impact Energy Absorbed}(J)}{\text{Thickness}(mm)} \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.2: Impact Energy Absorbed and Impact Strength of the Kevlar Polypropylene with varying Sawdust

The findings of the impact test show an intriguing pattern: as the amount of Kevlar or sawdust in the Polypropylene Matrix Composites increases, impact resistance steadily rises (PPCs). The 19.0 J/mm impact strength of Sample A increases progressively to an astounding 23.5 J/mm in Sample C, demonstrating a clear, positive relationship between impact performance and reinforcement concentration.

The improved resistance to impact can be ascribed to the Kevlar/Sawdust blend's capacity to effectively absorb and release impact energy. Kevlar's strong tensile strength and stiffness efficiently resist crack propagation, while the interlocking cellulose network within sawdust works as an energy-absorbing network. This improves impact performance by delaying material failure and reducing stress concentrations in a synergistic manner. According to a study by Yuan et al. (2017), polypropylene composites reinforced with 20 weight percent jute fibres showed a 32% improvement in impact strength, demonstrating the importance of natural fibres in boosting impact resistance.

Because of this impact energy dispersion, crack initiation and propagation are impeded, increasing resistance to abrupt force. Similar findings were reported by Dong (2020), who discovered that the addition of small glass fibres to a polypropylene matrix greatly increased the material's resistance to impact by deflecting and absorbing impact energy.

The impact test values are very important for determining whether or not the PPCs are suitable for demanding applications. Better resistance to external shocks and drops is shown by higher impact strength, which makes these composites perfect for usage in sports equipment, protection gear, and automobile parts. Optimizing the composite design for intended applications also heavily relies on knowing the impact behaviour through test values. Through optimization of the Kevlar/Sawdust ratio and investigation of substitute reinforcing materials, engineers can customise the impact resistance to meet particular needs.

4.2 Production Cost Analysis

Item	Quantity	Unit	Rate (₱)	Amount (₱)
Sawdust	1	kg	6,400	6,400
Aramid Kevlar Fabric (GSM 200)	1	m ²	28,000	28,000
Polypropylene Resin	1000	mL	6,500	6,500
Saline	500	mL	4,500	4,500
Grand Total				45,400:00

Further information about particular cost components is included in the cost breakdown that is given. Importation and shipping costs are included in the cost of Kevlar, raising the overall sum. In a similar vein, transportation costs are included in the price of the Polypropylene Resin and add to its overall cost. Pre-processing fees are an additional expense associated with sawdust, and they are included in the total cost. These additional charges connected with logistics, importation, and pre-processing are integrated into the individual material costs, representing the comprehensive expenses incurred throughout the procurement process for this composite fabrication project.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

A thorough analysis of the composite material's characteristics reveals a strong and adaptable substance that can satisfy a variety of application requirements. Its remarkable resistance to water absorption highlights its adaptability in damp situations. This resistance is demonstrated by the small weight gain and low percentage values (ranging from 0.56 percent to 0.79 percent). This intrinsic resistance, supported by research demonstrating comparable low absorption rates in composite materials, indicates the composite's potential for extended longevity and dependability across a range of circumstances. Furthermore, Kevlar/careful Sawdust's design and integration into the Polypropylene Matrix show not just a strategic approach to material engineering but also a synergy that strengthens the composite against outside influences.

Additionally, a strong trend showing a direct association between the amount of Kevlar or sawdust and material hardness is demonstrated by the Shore D Hardness Test. This steady increase in hardness values (from 83.5 in Sample A to an astounding 93.0 in Sample D) is in line with studies that highlight the influence of reinforcing chemicals on material hardness. The characteristics of the reinforcing blend—such as the interlocking nature of sawdust particles and the stiffness of Kevlar—help to greatly hinder plastic deformation, strengthening the composite against structural compromises.

Furthermore, an interesting trend of increasing impact resistance with increasing Kevlar/Sawdust content is revealed by the Impact Test results. The impact strength of Sample C is significantly

higher than that of Sample A (19.0 J/mm), indicating that the composite may find use in situations where resistance to sudden force is required. This increased resistance, which is a result of the blend's ability to effectively absorb and distribute impact energy, puts the composite in a favourable position in industries including sports equipment, protective gear, and automotive components. Comprehending this behaviour is essential for optimising the design of the composite, enabling engineers to customise its impact resistance to fulfil certain application needs.

All things considered, this composite material exhibits tremendous potential in a number of industries due to its remarkable water resistance, notable hardness improvements, and increased impact resistance. Its adaptability and ability to tolerate a range of climatic and force-related difficulties highlight its appropriateness for specialised applications requiring mechanical toughness, resilience, and durability.

5.2 Recommendations

In the engineering sector, the composite material shows promise in various applications:

- i. **Automotive Industry:** It can be applied to the production of impact-resistant auto parts, such as bumpers and structural components.
- ii. **Development of Protective Gear:** To produce robust sports equipment, body armour, or helmets that can endure unexpected shocks.
- iii. **Construction:** It works well with sturdy, moisture-resistant building materials that may be used for a variety of construction tasks.

As for further development:

- i. Further research can be done to modify the composition of the composite for certain applications by experimenting with varying ratios of sawdust to kevlar.
- ii. Investigating whether incorporating additional materials enhances or introduces new properties to the composite
- iii. evaluating the composite's performance in various settings or under various forces in order to tailor it to a given task or set of circumstances.

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APPENDICES

We have 100,000 square metres of aramid fabric in stock
 Please contact customer service for specific grammage specifications before placing your order, here are samples of aramid fabric,we welcome bulk orders
 The customer service Whatsapp:+8613677735785

Specificaion:

UNXDEFENCE filament fibres are para-aramids made from the condensation of p-phenylenediamine and p-phenylene terephthalate chloride. UNXDEFENCE filament fibres have a golden yellow appearance, low relative density and high strength, with a specific strength six times that of steel wire, and are therefore widely used in high-end applications such as tyres, fibre optic cables, ballistic protection, high speed railways and aerospace. In addition, UNXDEFENCE filament fibres have good flame retardancy and thermal stability, and are able to maintain performance degradation at 200C within 20%, so they are also used in high temperature protection, friction and sealing.

General specifications:

100/200/400/600/800/1000/1500/3000D

Model	Denier	Warp*Weft/cm	GSM	Thickness	Width/MM	Warp	Weft	Length/M
AP1	3000	13.5*13.5	80	0.08	500-3000	≥1.6	≥1.5	100
AP2	4000	12.0*12.0	80	0.11	500-3000	≥2.0	≥2.0	100
AP3	4000	13.5*13.5	120	0.14	500-3000	≥2.6	≥2.7	100
AP4	6000	8.0*8.0	180	0.15	500-3000	≥2.5	≥2.6	100
AP5	8400	8.5*8.5	180	0.25	500-3000	≥3.6	≥3.8	100
AP6	8400	10.5*10.5	260	0.30	500-3000	≥4.0	≥4.2	100
AP7	10000	6.0*6.0	140	0.22	500-3000	≥3.5	≥3.6	100
AP8	10000	7.0*7.0	180	0.24	500-3000	≥3.0	≥3.2	100
AP9	10000	9.0*9.0	300	0.26	500-3000	≥3.8	≥4.0	100
AP10	10000	11.5*11.5	255	0.31	500-3000	≥4.8	≥5.2	100
AP11	10000	13.5*13.5	270	0.34	500-3000	≥5.0	≥5.3	100
AP12	15000	5.0*5.0	170	0.23	500-3000	≥3.3	≥3.5	100
AP13	15000	6.0*6.0	300	0.26	500-3000	≥3.6	≥4.2	100
AP14	15000	12.7*12.7	410	0.62	500-3000	≥7.2	≥8.2	100
AP15	18000	6.5*6.5	460	0.68	500-3000	≥8.2	≥8.5	100

IMPACT
Aramid specification list

序号	克重 (g/平方) gram weight gsm	纱线规格 Specification of yarn	幅宽 Width	纹路 grain		厚度mm Thickness	经密 Warp	纬密 weft	米长 Lenders	收卷内径 inner diameter
1	400	3000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.55±0.1	6±1	5±1	50-200	3inch
2	300	3000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.45±0.1	5±1	4±1	50-200	3inch
3	200	1500D	30-320	plain	twill	0.26±0.05	6±1	5.5±1	50-400	3inch
4	220	1500D	30-320	plain	twill	0.26±0.05	6±1	6±1	50-400	3inch
5	240	1500D	30-320	plain	twill	0.28±0.05	6±1	6.5±1	50-400	3inch
6	200	1000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.25±0.05	9±1	9±1	50-400	3inch
7	270	1000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.32±0.05	13±1	11±1	50-400	3inch
8	180	1000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.23±0.05	9±1	7.5±1	50-400	3inch
9	145	800D	30-320	plain	twill	0.18±0.05	8±1	8±1	50-400	3inch
10	340g	1500D	30-320	plain	twill	0.42±0.1	11±1	9±1	50-400	3inch
11	420	3000D	30-320	plain	twill	0.6±0.1	6±1	5±1	50-200	3inch
12	230	202	30-300		w	0.5±0.1	20±2	14±2	50-400	3inch
13	500	1414+1500	30-320	plain	twill	0.7±0.1	7±1	5±1	50-400	3inch
14	60	200D	30-320	plain	twill	0.1±0.03	14±1	13±1	50-400	3inch
15	80	400D	30-320	plain	twill	0.14±0.03			50-400	3inch
16	230	204	30-300	plain	twill				50-400	3inch
17		Spun aramid filament yarn		cross woven					50-400	3inch

COMMERCIAL INVOICE

商业发票

WAYBILL NO (单号) : 8142186673

number (件数) : 1

weight (重量) kg: 1.368

托运备注:

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SHIPPER DETAILS (寄件人信息):

COMPANY NAME (公司名): Damilare Lekan Adekoye	COMPANY NAME (公司名): SHANGHAI QEP INTERNATIONAL
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CITY (城市): Bosso	CITY (城市): DUBAI
province (省):	province (省):
COUNTRY (国家): Nigeria	COUNTRY (国家):
mobile phone (手机): +2348163180829	mobile phone (手机):
POSTCODE (邮编): 920211	POSTCODE (邮编):
CONTACT NAME (联系人): Damilare Lekan Adekoye	CONTACT NAME (联系人): SUI ZHENG WEI
TELEPHONE (电话):	TELEPHONE (电话): 043525050

Cargo information (货物信息):

客户订单号: 8142186673

description of the goods (货物描述)	PCS 数量	ORIGIN 产地	UNIT VALUE (USD) 单价	TOTAL VAL (USD) 总价值
芳纶布: 5007202900 Aramid fabric	1		30.00	30.00
TOTAL (总计): USD				30

SHIPPER'S SIGNATURE & STAMP:
托运人的签名及盖章

DATE:
日期: 2023-10-20